

SensApp

D1.7 International Symposium

Grant Agreement Number	829104
Project Name	Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach
Project Acronym	SensApp
Start date of the project	01/01/2019
End date of the project	30/06/2022 (6-months extension)
Work package producing the document	WP1 – Management and dissemination
Deliverable identifier	D1.7
Nature of deliverable	Websites, patents filling, etc.
Lead beneficiary	CNR
Contributors	All participants
Dissemination level	PU (Public)
Author(s)	Veronica Vespini, Sara Coppola, Simonetta Grilli
Version	V1.0
Due date	30 June 2021
Delivery date	1 July 2021

Simonetta Grilli (CNR) and Pietro Ferraro (CNR) are the co-chairs of the SPIE Conference 11786 “Optical Methods for Inspection, Characterization, and Imaging of Biomaterials V” held in the framework of the international Symposium “SPIE Optical Metrology”, which takes place in Munich (Germany) every two years. Here is the link to the general event: <https://spie.org/conferences-and-exhibitions/optical-metrology>. This event highlights the latest advances in optical measurement systems. It is the meeting for emerging photonics fields within measurement systems, modelling, imaging, sensing, and inspection.

As co-chair of the above-mentioned conference Simonetta Grilli and co-workers (CNR) organized together with the SPIE staff the International Symposium dedicated to the topics of SensApp in the framework of this SPIE event, to have the opportunity to reach many researchers coming from universities, research centres and companies all over the world. This year the conference was held from 21st to 25th of June 2021 as a virtual online event, due to the COVID-related emergency. The program schedule was based on the Central European Summer Time (CEST, UTC+02:00). The feedback on the SensApp Project results was very positive, reaching various researchers around the world.

About SPIE, the international society for optics and photonics

SPIE. OPTICAL METROLOGY Attend Programme Presenters 21-25 June 2021 Online Only Register

SPIE Optical Metrology
A digital forum for the latest research in measurement systems, modeling, videometrics, and inspection

Registration Programme

Featuring all the great content you expect at SPIE Optical Metrology

The World of Photonics Congress, which includes SPIE Optical Metrology, will be held as a virtual, online event. The program schedule is based on Central European Summer Time (CEST, UTC+02:00). This event highlights the latest advances in optical measurement systems. It is the meeting for emerging photonics fields within modeling, imaging, sensing, and inspection.

#SPIEOpticalMetrology

- SPIE, the international society for optics and photonics, was founded in 1955 to advance light-based technologies
- Serving more than 255,000 constituents from 183 countries, the not-for-profit society advances emerging technologies through interdisciplinary information exchange, continuing education, publications, patent precedent, and career and professional growth
- SPIE annually organizes and sponsors approximately 25 major technical forums, exhibitions, and education programs in North America, Europe, Asia, and the South Pacific
- In 2020, SPIE provided more than \$5 million in support of education and outreach programs

SPIE Optical Metrology 2021 programme

- Live plenary talks
- Technical presentations
- Networking sessions

Optical Metrology programme

The Optical Metrology Symposium consisted of a powerful week with different conferences and special events, as illustrated by the screenshot below.

Browse Optical Metrology programme
Find events and build your schedule

All
Conferences
Presentations
Special Events

Filter By | [Clear All](#)

Date —

Monday, 21 June (6)

Tuesday, 22 June (6)

Wednesday, 23 June (6)

Thursday, 24 June (6)

Friday, 25 June (6)

Technical Track —

Optical Metrology (6)

6 results found. Sort By: Program Number ▾

Conference 11782

Optical Measurement Systems for Industrial Inspection XII
Chair(s): Peter Lehmann; Wolfgang Osten; Armando Albertazzi Gonçalves Jr.
▶ On-demand starting 21 June

Conference 11783

Modeling Aspects in Optical Metrology VIII
Chair(s): Bernd Bodermann; Karsten Frenner; Bryan M. Barnes
▶ On-demand starting 21 June

Conference 11784

Optics for Arts, Architecture, and Archaeology (O3A) VIII
Chair(s): Haida Liang; Roger Groves
▶ On-demand starting 21 June

Conference 11785

Multimodal Sensing and Artificial Intelligence: Technologies and Applications II
Chair(s): Ettore Stella; Shahriar Negahdaripour; Dariusz Ceglarek; Christian Möller
▶ On-demand starting 21 June

Conference 11786

Optical Methods for Inspection, Characterization, and Imaging of Biomaterials V
Chair(s): Pietro Ferraro; Simonetta Grilli; Monika Ritsch-Marte; Christoph K. Hitzengerger
▶ On-demand starting 21 June

The red arrow indicates in particular the above mentioned conference “Optical Methods for Inspection, Characterization, and Imaging of Biomaterials V”, which includes the special event “FET-Open on disruptive ideas and optical technologies for health” (see below).

Conference 11786

Optical Methods for Inspection, Characterization, and Imaging of Biomaterials V

Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Add to My Schedule

Presentations

Chairs and Committees

View Session ^

Welcome and Introduction

11786-800
Welcome and Introduction to SPIE Conference 11786
 Author(s): Pietro Ferraro, Simonetta Grilli, Istituto di Scienze Applicate e Sistemi Intelligenti "Eduardo
 Medizinsche Univ. Innsbruck (Austria); Christoph K. F. Hitzemberger, Medizinische Univ. Wien (Austria)
 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Session PL: Optical Metrology Plenary Session

11782-500
Optical sociology: how organizational culture impacts advances in optical metrology (
 Author(s): Peter J. de Groot, Zygo Corporation (United States)
 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June
 Show Abstract +

Session 1: Imaging in Microfluidics

11786.1

- Welcome and Introduction
- Optical Metrology Plenary Session
- 1: Imaging in Microfluidics
- 2: Digital Holographic Microscopy I
- 3: Digital Holographic Microscopy II
- 4: Micromanipulation
- 5: Biomaterial Fabrication
- 6: Phase Microscopy and Tomography
- 7: Tissue Imaging
- 8: Imaging
- 9: Biophotonics and Additive Manufacturing Technologies for 3D Health Monitoring
- 10: Scaffolds and Advanced Materials
- 11: FET-Open on Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health**
- Poster Session

Session 11: FET-Open on Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health

This special event presented keynote talks from research leaders all over Europe involved in FET-Open funded projects which topics are related to Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health. In particular, the organisers invited 6 keynote speakers and the event was held as a plenary “special live event” in the SPIE Optical Metrology Symposium, as illustrated by the screenshot below.

Future & Emerging Technologies-Open on Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health I

22 June 2021 • 11:00 - 13:05 CEST **LIVE EVENT**

Add to My Schedule

Shaping Europe’s digital future: join us in exploring how the Future & Emerging Technologies (FET) programme invests in transformative frontier research and innovation with a high potential impact on technology, to benefit our economy and society.

The program included also one keynote speaker coming from the European Innovation Council. Overall, the event was appreciated a lot with lots of participants from many countries all over the world. During the day program, the SensApp project coordinator (Simonetta Grilli) gave a speech in this session illustrating the overview of SensApp, the motivations and the intermediate results, SensApp has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 829104. www.sensapp.eu

without disclosing confidential contents, in order to disseminate as much as possible the SensApp activities.

The image below shows the list of the keynote talks of this FET-Open live session, which included FET-Open funded projects dealing with topics related to the development of technologies for health applications:

Session 11: FET-Open on Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health ^

11786-57

 From FET to EIC-Pathfinder (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Ioannis Fiamegkos, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) (Belgium)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-58

 SensApp: a FET-open project for developing a supersensor able to detect Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in blood (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Simonetta Grilli, Istituto di Scienze Applicate e Sistemi Intelligenti "Eduardo Caianiello" (Italy)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-59

 Connecting brain and artificial neurons with nanoscale brain-inspired devices (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Stefano Vassanelli, Univ. degli Studi di Padova (Italy)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-60

 IN2SIGHT: an in vivo bioengineered chip for new validation protocols of biomaterials (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Giuseppe Chirico, Univ. degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca (Italy)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-61

 A step forward to spinal cord injury repair using innovative stimulated nanoengineered scaffolds (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Paula Marques, University of Aveiro (Portugal)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-62

 SHERO: Self-healing Soft Robotics (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Joost Brancart, Seppe Terryn, Guy Van Assche, Vrije Univ. Brussel (Belgium); François Tournhilhac, Ecole Supérieure de Physique et de Chimie Industrielles de la Ville de Paris (France); Frank Clemens, EMPA (Switzerland); Fumiya Iida, Univ. of Cambridge (United Kingdom); Anton W. Bosman, SupraPolix B.V. (Netherlands); Bram Vanderborght, Vrije Univ. Brussel (Belgium)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

11786-66

 Detection of chemiluminescence-induced photosensitizer activation through fluorescence and concomitant singlet oxygen generation (Invited Paper)

Author(s): Mantas Grigalavicius, Kristian Berg, Theodossis A. Theodossiou, Oslo Univ. Hospital (Norway)

 Digital Forum: On-demand starting 21 June

Show Abstract +

The red arrow indicates the talk from SensApp coordinator Simonetta Grilli and the image below shows the title page of her presentation.

The event was highly appreciated by the participants for all interesting case studies presented. Other SensApp partners also contributed with their work to the conference. It was a good opportunity to meet online users and researchers to discuss the latest inventions and applications in the field of Disruptive Ideas and Optical Technologies for Health. Moreover, the invited keynote speaker Ioannis Fiamegkos, from European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) (Belgium), presented the keynote talk **“From FET to EIC-Pathfinder”** aiming to illustrate the diverse portfolio of targeted projects that explore wide-ranging technological potential, inspired by cutting-edge science, unconventional collaboration, and innovative practices.

We show below a screenshot of the digital event during the countdown before the start of the session.

The images below are taken from the SPIE Optical Metrology website and illustrate the abstracts of the talks and the short biographies of the keynote speakers. The SPIE website keeps the link to the recorded presentation from each speaker.

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the video recording in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

From FET to EIC-Pathfinder

Ioannis Flamegkos, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) (Belgium)

The European Innovation Council (EIC) is Europe's flagship innovation programme aiming to identify, develop and scale up breakthrough technologies and game-changing innovations. EIC has been established under the EU Horizon Europe programme and it has a budget of €10 billion. The aim is to support game-changing innovations from early stage research, to proof of concept, technology transfer, and the financing and scale up of start-ups and SMEs. The EIC takes a proactive approach to managing funding by developing the visions for innovation and technology breakthroughs and by steering the portfolio of projects to achieve these goals. In this new environment the well-known FET is transformed to EIC Pathfinder (with the Pathfinder Open and Pathfinder Challenges calls) aiming to develop a diverse portfolio of targeted projects that explore wide-ranging technological potential, inspired by cutting-edge science, unconventional collaboration and innovative practices. Grants of up to 3 to 4 million euros support early stage development of future technologies for various activities at low Technology Readiness Levels 1-3, up to proof of concept. Pathfinder projects can also receive additional funding for testing the innovation potential of their research outputs.

Biography: **Ioannis Flamegkos** is an Analytical Chemist, being an active researcher for more than 20 years (literature name: Yvanis Flamegkos). His research has focused on the development and validation of analytical methods mainly for the determination of small molecules in a variety of samples. In 2018 he moved to the Research Executive Agency of the European Commission as a Project Adviser of the FET-OPEN funding scheme. With the transfer of the FET-OPEN to the newly established European Innovation Council he found himself in EISMEA and the Pathfinder-Open and Pathfinder-Challenges funding schemes.

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the video recording in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

Connecting brain and artificial neurons with nanoscale brain-inspired devices

Stefano Vassanelli, Univ. degli Studi di Padova (Italy)

Neural probes for electrical imaging and microstimulation of brain networks represent an ideal communication gateway between nanoelectronic devices emulating neuron computation and biological neurons. We show that titanium oxide microelectrodes and memristors can establish synaptic-like connections between biological and silicon spiking neurons across an elementary biohybrid network.

Biography: **Stefano Vassanelli** is professor of Neurophysiology at the University of Padova, Dept. of Biomedical Sciences and Padua Neuroscience Center, and leader of the NeuroChip laboratory. His main research focus is the development of neural probes and AI technologies for brain-machine interfacing and for the investigation of information processing in brain microcircuits. He is currently coordinating the SYNCH project founded by the European Commission under the H2020 FET Proactive programme aiming at the creation of a hybrid biological-artificial neural architecture with memristive plasticity in vivo.

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the recorded video in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

A step forward to spinal cord injury repair using innovative stimulated nanoengineered scaffolds

Paula Marques, University of Aveiro (Portugal)

The goal of NeuroStimSpinal FETOPEN project is to contribute with a solution for spinal cord injury (SCI). Considering the biological complexity of SCI, a small incremental discovery in this area may represent an improvement that will translate into better clinical care and in the quality of life of these patients. Therefore, a neural tissue engineered scaffold capable of not only combining fibrous and porous topographic cues in order to mimic the morphology of the native spinal cord, but also potentiating the properties of graphenebased materials supported in a protein-rich decellularized matrix is being developed to be coupled with a wireless electrical stimulation device to promote the growth and reconnection of the ruptured nerves. This communication will cover the challenge and the progresses obtained so far.

Biography: **Paula Marques** is tenured scientist at the University of Aveiro, Department of Mechanical Engineering. Her main research interest is dedicated to development of smart 3D nanostructured materials for health and environmental applications, respectively tissue engineering and water remediation. She is currently coordinating the NeuroStimSpinal project, a H2020-FETOPEN project aiming at creating a stimulus responsive scaffold for spinal cord injuries treatment.

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the video recording in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

SensApp: a FET-open project for developing a supersensor able to detect Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in blood

Simonetta Grilli, Istituto di Scienze Applicate e Sistemi Intelligenti "Eduardo Ciianelli" (Italy)

The goal of SensApp FET-Open project is to develop an innovative super-sensor that will be able to detect Alzheimer's disease (AD) biomarkers (β-amyloid, Tau and pTAU) in peripheral blood. Considering that nowadays an accurate diagnosis of AD requires the highly invasive withdrawal and analysis of cerebrospinal fluid, SensApp will represent a breakthrough in the field of AD diagnosis thanks to the ability to detect the early stage of the disease by a simple blood collection. We call Droplet-Split-and-Stack (DSS) the new technology that will emerge from SensApp. The achievement of SensApp goal will be insured by the interdisciplinary cooperation between different research institutions and one company involved in the key fields of the project, Vrije University of Brussels, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, University of Linz, Gintilis Ltd, IRCCS Centre "Borromeo Pulejo", under the coordination of CNR-Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems. This communication will illustrate the progress of the activities. Acknowledgments: The authors acknowledge the EU funding within the Horizon 2020 Program, under the FET-OPEN Project "SensApp", Grant Agreement n.829104.

Biography: **Simonetta Grilli** got her PhD at the KTH in Stockholm and she is now a research scientist at CNR-INO. Her current activities include nanostructuring of ferroelectric crystals and nanomanipulation of fluids through pyro-electrohydrodynamic approaches. She received the Doctoral Thesis Award in Optoelectronics from the IEEE-LEOS society. She is co-author of more than 60 papers in international journals. She is co-editor of the book Ferroelectric Crystals for Photonic Applications by Springer (2008).

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the recorded video in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

IN2SIGHT: an in vivo bioengineered chip for new validation protocols of biomaterials

Giuseppe Chirico, Univ. degli Studi di Milano-Bicocca (Italy)

I will review the fundamental limiting issues in in-vivo optical imaging and discuss the proposal made by the IN2SIGHT consortium to overcome them and its impact. IN2SIGHT will foster a breakthrough in in-vivo optical imaging that will renovate the biocompatibility tests (ISO10993 EU norm) required for the development of biomaterials for clinical use. These tests are economical and ethical unsustainable for small-medium industries and for the society. The IN2SIGHT approach stands on a micro-structured chip that will recast our thinking of deep tissue in-vivo imaging. I discuss how this proposal will allow unique quantification of the immune reaction to biomaterials, thus reducing time and costs for testing with a potential huge impact on public health systems and our society. The project sees the collaboration of seven partners from five countries and will exploit from the beginning inter-sector approaches in an interdisciplinary environment.

Biography: **Giuseppe Chirico** received his PhD in biophysics in 1990. He was research associate at the European Molecular Laboratory in Grenoble (F) and at the German Cancer Research Center (DKFZ) in Heidelberg. He is currently professor of Applied Physics at the University of Milano-Bicocca, Milano (I). His activity covers biophysics, photonics and nanotechnology: fluorescence correlation spectroscopies applied to biological systems, in-vivo deep tissue imaging and fabrication of proteinaceous microstructures by means of non-linear excitation.

This event occurred in the past.

[Click here to view the recorded video in the SPIE Digital Library.](#)

SHERO: Self-healing Soft Robotics

Joost Brancart, Vrije Univ. Brussel (Belgium):

Soft robotic systems benefit from improved compliance and larger degrees of freedom, allowing more complex motions and safer interaction with their environment than rigid robotic structures. Due to the inherent softness of the materials that are often used to create such soft robotic structures, these systems are highly susceptible to various damage modes, such as cuts or punctures by sharp objects, overloading during actuation, flaws originating from manufacturing process or fatigue failure, drastically limiting their service lifetimes. Various types of synthetic materials that possess the ability to repair damage, are being used to create soft robotic systems that are able to recover their performance by repairing incurred damage, either autonomously or after the application of a stimulus. The breakthrough targeted in the SHERO project is the development of complete robotic systems that are able to (1) sense and locate damage and to evaluate the system performance, (2) react intelligently to alleviate the damaging event and prevent catastrophic failure, (3) take the necessary measures to heal the damage to restore all functions by facilitating an autonomous or controlled healing action of the damaged element, and (4) perform a rehabilitation by evaluating the quality of the healing process and the recovery of functional performance, and finally, (5) return to action.

Biography: Dr. **Joost Brancart** obtained his PhD in 2017 from the Vrije Universiteit Brussel for his research on stimuli-responsive materials for self-healing applications. He actively explores the use of temperature, light and mechanical force to establish reversible polymer network formation and for the activation of reversible material responses. In 2018, he was granted a postdoctoral scholarship from the Research Foundation - Flanders (FWO) to expand his work towards self-healing composites, focusing on electrically conductive and magnetic composites. Currently he is co-coordinating the EU-funded FET Open SHERO and Marie-Curie action SMART. He is leading a team of material scientists and mechanical engineers covering the development of new stimuli-responsive materials, their characterization, processing and manufacturing until the evaluation and validation in various robotic applications.

This event occurred in the past.

Click [here](#) to view the recorded video in the SPIE Digital Library.

Detection of chemiluminescence-induced photosensitizer activation through fluorescence and concomitant singlet oxygen generation

Theodoros A. Theodoros, Oslo Univ. Hospital (Norway)

In the course of experiments for our FET open project Lumiblast, we set off to measure the excitation of various photoactive drugs (photosensitizers, PS) by the luminescence emission of luminol. Luminol (5-Amino-2,2-dihydrophthalazine-1(4H)-one) is a chemical that interacts with reactive oxygen species (ROS) in basic conditions, and in the presence of metal catalysts like Fe or Cu, gives out a characteristic blue luminescence. When dissolved in organic solvents like DMSO, however, luminol only requires the addition of bases like KOH, NaOH or potassium tertbutoxide, to fulfil the conditions for luminescence emission. In the present work we employed a detection system based on a spectrograph coupled to a CCD camera to register fluorescence (Fig.1B) or luminescence (Fig.1A, C). In the case of characteristic fluorescence registration (Fig.1B), the PS investigated were excited by a 532 nm laser with a variable power output. We have documented the energy transfer from chemically induced luminol luminescence to a number of PSs including rose bengal, erythrosin B, hypericin amongst others. In all cases both the luminol emission and the luminol luminescence-induced PS fluorescence were registered as shown in the example of luminol and erythrosin B in Fig.1C. We further attempted to register the generation of singlet oxygen from luminol-excited PSs. To achieve this, we employed the near-infrared (NIR) photomultiplier tube (PMT) shown in Fig.1E, with a cut-off filter at 900nm and a bandpass filter at 1270±30 nm. This allowed only radiation within this spectral region to reach the PMT, corresponding to the characteristic phosphorescence of singlet oxygen, spin forbidden de-excitation to ground state triplet oxygen. A characteristic steady state singlet oxygen registration can be seen in Fig. 1D, for erythrosin B which has a high singlet oxygen quantum yield. The luminol luminescence was initiated by addition of tertbutoxide to the DMSO luminol solution, at which point we can see a rise of the signal at 1270 nm. Upon addition of the singlet oxygen quencher, L-histidine, the signal dropped steadily to background levels. NOTE: Figures are not available.

Biography: **Theo Theodoros** is a project group leader at the Department of Radiation Biology, Institute for Cancer Research, Oslo University Hospital, Oslo, Norway, where he is currently affiliated since 2013. After finishing his PhD in 1995 in nuclear/atomic physics, Dr. Theodoros has worked on photomedicine, nanotechnology, bioenergetics with emphasis on cell mitochondria and the electron transport chain, nonlinear tissue optics, and radiation biology. After his PhD studies he completed his first postdoc at the National Technical University of Athens (1997-2001) then he worked as a researcher at University College London (2001-2006) and NCSR Demokritos (2006-2013). Dr. Theodoros has additionally worked as a clinical scientist in photodynamic therapies on various cancer indications at UCL hospitals, NHS Trust (2002-2004). He has served in the Website committee and the Strategic alliances and outreach committee of the Society for Free Radicals in Biology and Medicine (SFRBM). He has also been a member of the Publications, Grants and Awards committees and chair of the Strategic Planning Committee of the American Society for Photobiology (ASP). Dr. Theodoros has initiated, written and coordinated one Marie Curie Intra-European Fellowship, one Euronanomed and two Future and Emerging Technologies (FET-open) projects (2013-2021). One of the FET-open projects, "Lumiblast", received the European innovative science award, in 2019. Dr. Theodoros was proclaimed institute researcher of the year (2019), while he was awarded the Ragnar Mark prize for outstanding research in 2020.

The special event was also disclosed and advertised by using the social accounts of SensApp on Twitter, Facebook and Instagram. Some related screenshots are shown below as example:

Moreover, the recorded presentation of Simonetta Grilli was uploaded on the YouTube channel of SensApp: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dHvsK8fyyME>

In conclusion, the international symposium of SensApp was organised in the large international framework of the SPIE Optical Metrology Symposium with the opportunity to reach researchers coming from all over the world and working on topics familiar with those of SensApp. This event permitted to raise further awareness of the project.